

THERAPEUTIC EFFECTS OF COGNITIVE RESTRUCTURING ON POST-TRAUMATIC STRESS AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN BAUCHI, NIGERIA

Okonkwo, Ifeanyi Chukwudi

National Open University of Nigeria
University Village, Plot 91, Cadastral
Zone, Nnamdi Azikiwe Expressway,
Jabi –Abuja

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Abstract

Post-traumatic stress disorder is one of the conditions that affect students' psychological, sociological and overall functioning including of students at the tertiary level. Insecurity issues in Nigeria, particularly, in North East, is a major concern that resulted to different challenges that throw the undergraduate students in to different and ugly traumatic conditions that often leads students to depression, anxiety, low self-esteem, sleepless nights, isolation, confusion, unsecure, fear, unhealthy relationships, among others and even thinking of committing suicide. This scenario constitutes the main interest of this research. The aim of this research therefore, was to ascertain the effects of Cognitive Restructuring Therapy on University undergraduate students with Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder in ATBU Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to determine the extent to which students suffer from PTSD, how PTSD interferes on students' psychological, sociological and overall functioning and the effect of PTSD based on gender. For the purpose of data collection, PTSD screening scale was used to collect data that was used before and after treatment with Cognitive Restructuring Therapy and its effects on PTSD was assessed.

Keyword: Trauma Recovery, Trauma-Informed Care, Stress Disorder Management, Mental Health Intervention

INTRODUCTION

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is one of the conditions that affect students' psychological, sociological and overall development at the tertiary level. As a result of the Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder found among University undergraduate students occasioned by different encounter with issues of life, at different levels of different traumatic situations, ranging from war and conflict, torture,

armed robbery, kidnapping, boko haram, Fulani herdsmen killings of innocent souls, serious fatal accidents, plane crash, physical or sexual assault and abuse. Other forms of traumatic experience include childhood or domestic abuse, chronic health challenges, weather related disaster like flood that happens in many parts of Nigeria, ethnicity conflict among others. These ugly trends throw the students into psychological disorders resulting to mental health

problems and dysfunction that affects almost every aspect of the students' life and development. Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) also occurs when undergraduate students lose their loved ones, as a result of violence, and bomb explosions that occurred in many vicinities of Nigerian societies, particularly the NorthEastern part of the country. Furthermore, crisis in various places, killing of innocent students by cult members, religious crisis, chieftaincy tussle, insurgency, bullying and public coercion, among others are all sources of traumatic events confronting University undergraduate students which at the end interfere with the students' psychological, physiological and sociological adjustments resulting to some psychological and mental disorders.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to find out effects of cognitive restructuring counselling therapy on University undergraduate students with post-traumatic stress disorder in Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU) Bauchi State, Nigeria. The specific Objective is to:

1. determine the PTSD mean scores of undergraduate students before and after exposure to Cognitive Restructuring Counselling therapy in the experimental group and control group.
2. determine the PTSD interference mean score of the experimental group and control group before and after exposure to Cognitive Restructuring Counselling therapy

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions have been raised to guide the study:

1. What are the pre-test and post-test post-traumatic stress disorder mean scores of undergraduate students in the experimental and control groups?
2. What are the pre-test and post-test post-traumatic stress disorder interference mean scores of the undergraduate students between the experimental group and control group?

HYPOTHESES

The following hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the post-test post-traumatic stress disorders mean score of undergraduate students in the experimental group and control group.
2. There is no significant difference between the post-test post-traumatic stress disorder interference mean scores of undergraduate students in the experimental group and control group.

METHOD

This research adopts quasi-experimental research design, specifically the nonequivalent pre-test, post-test design. This design allows for a pre-test before treatment is implemented and the post-test after the treatment has been implemented for experimental group. The population of this study consisted of all the 200 level full-time undergraduate students in Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi. Only two (2) Departments in ATBU and one Unit from each Department were used for this study. The two (2) Departments are Department of Vocational Technology and Department of Science Education. The two (2) Units were Business Education Unit of Department of Vocational Technology Education and Agricultural Science Education of the Department of Science Education. The sample for this study was made up of sixty 200 level undergraduate students. There were thirty one (31) students in Business Education Unit of Department of Vocational Technology Education Faculty of Technology Education and twenty nine (29) students from Agricultural Science Education of the Department of Science Education respectively. The total populations in the two (2) Units were sixty (60) students.

One instrument was used for data collection for this research which is Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder PTSD Screening Scale (PTSDSS). The instrument was used for pre-test and post-test to measure the level or stage of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder of the sample before and after exposure to Cognitive Restructuring Therapy in the experimental and control groups. The Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Screening Scale is divided into two sections, A and B. Section A consisted of the bio data of the students

such as gender, course, and level while section B, consisted of seventeen (17) item with other questions attached that help guide the students in making decision with regards to the scale. The grading system is a 5 point Likert scale. The choice of 5 point Likert scale in this study is informed by the fact that it is used by researchers to measure attitudes, knowledge, perceptions, values, and behavioural changes. A Likert scale involves a series of statements that respondents may choose from in order to rate their responses to evaluative questions. The researcher employed the 5 Likert scale of 1-Never, 2- Rarely, 3-Sometimes, 4- Often, and 5- Always to ascertain the frequency level of the students' responses to traumatic experience. An agreement with item like Never attracts one

(0) point, Rarely attracts two (2) points; Sometimes attracts three (3) points; Often attracts four (4) points

Table 1 Results of the Pretest and Posttest Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Mean Scores between the Experimental and Control Group

Group	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain /Loss	\bar{x} - difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Experimental	31	62.48	13.11	28.23	7.73	-34.25	-34.52
Control	29	60.83	13.30	61.10	12.93	0.27	

Table 1 reveals the pre-test and post-test post-traumatic stress disorder mean score of University undergraduate students in the experimental group and control group. In the experimental group the post-test post-traumatic stress disorder mean score was 28.23 and standard deviation of 7.73, lower than the pre-test mean score of 62.48 and standard deviation of 13.11 with a mean loss of -34.25, indicating that, there was reduction in the post-traumatic stress disorder of students after treatment. Also, for the control group the mean score was 60.38 and a standard deviation of 13.30 at the pretest. The post-test mean score of students was 61.10 and a standard deviation of 12.93. The findings show that students in the experimental group had a lower mean score (28.23) after treatment using cognitive restructuring counselling therapy than

and Always five (5) points. Respondents were carefully explained how to tick items from those options that best express their minds or feelings. The students without any difficulty were able to tick from options listed ones that best described their feelings. The instrument was administered to the respondents. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were deployed for the data analysis. Thus, mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions raised, and the researcher analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance

RESULTS Research Question One

What are the pre-test and post-test post-traumatic stress disorder mean score of University undergraduate students in the experimental group and control group

those in the control group (61.10) who were not given treatment with a mean difference of -34.52. This means that at the pre-test the students in both groups had a high posttraumatic stress disorder, but after the intervention there was a reduction in the post-traumatic stress disorder of the experimental group than the control group. It can be deduced that cognitive restructuring counselling therapy does reduce post-traumatic stress disorder of students.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the post-test post-traumatic stress disorder means scores of undergraduate university students in the experimental group and control group.

Table 2:**ANCOVA Results on the Post Test Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder of Undergraduate Students in the Experimental and Control Groups**

Source	Type III sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Partial squared	Eta squared
Corrected model	18173.447 ^a	2	9086.724	115.233	.000	.802	
Intercept	770.726	1	770.726	9.774	.003	.146	
Covariate	1977.373	1	1977.373	25.076	.000	.306	
Treatment	16857.259	1	16857.259	213.775	.000	.789	
Error	4494.736	57	78.855				
Total	139445.000	60					
Corrected total	22668.183	59					

a. R Squared = .802(Adjusted R Squared = .795)

The results of the ANCOVA analysis from Table 2 reveals the post-test mean scores of the post-traumatic stress disorder mean scores of undergraduate students between the experimental and control groups. The results indicates that $F(1, 57) = 213.78, p < 0.05$, since the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a significant effect of cognitive restructuring counselling therapy on undergraduate students' post-traumatic stress disorder mean scores. The results further reveal an adjusted R squared value of .795 which means that 79.5% of the variation in the

dependent variable which is post-traumatic stress disorder is explained by variation in the treatment of cognitive restructuring counselling therapy, while the remaining 20.5% is due to other factors not included in this study. This implies that cognitive restructuring counselling therapy can reduce undergraduate students post-traumatic stress disorder.

Research Question Two:

What are the pre-test and post-test post-traumatic stress disorder interference mean scores of undergraduate students between the experimental group and control group.

Table 3 The results of the pre-test and post-test PTSD interference mean scores between the experimental group and control group

Group	Pre-test			Post-test		Mean Gain /Loss	\bar{x} - difference
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Experimental	31	15.23	2.012	6.74	2.05	-8.49	-8.01
Control	29	15.14	1.747	14.66	1.587	-0.48	

Table 3 reveals the pre-test and post-test post-traumatic stress disorder interference means scores of undergraduate students between the experimental and control groups. In the experimental group the post-traumatic stress disorder interference mean score was 6.74 and standard deviation of 1.05, lower than the pre-test mean score of 15.23 and standard deviation of 2.01 with a mean loss of -8.49, indicating that there

was reduction in the post-traumatic stress disorder interference of students after treatment. Also, for the control group the mean score was 15.14 and a standard deviation of 1.75 at the pretest. The post-test mean score of students was 14.66 and a standard deviation of 1.59. The findings show that students in the experimental group had a lower mean score (6.74) after treatment using cognitive restructuring

counselling therapy than those in the control group (14.66) who were not given treatment with a mean difference of -8.01. This means that at the pre-test the students in both groups had high post-traumatic stress disorder interference, but after the intervention there was a reduction in the post-traumatic stress disorder interference of the experimental group than the control group. It can be deduced that cognitive restructuring counselling therapy does reduce post-traumatic stress disorder interference of students. This implies that cognitive restructuring counselling therapy help to reduce the undergraduate students' post-traumatic stress disorder interference in Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi, Bauchi State.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant difference between the post-test post-traumatic stress disorder interference means scores of undergraduate students in the experimental and control groups.

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